

Review

ESG Indices Research Domain: A Bibliometric Analysis of the Economics and Business Literature

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Abstract: *Over the past two decades, there has been a significant trend in stakeholders' request for greater transparency regarding corporate environmental, social and governance (ESG) performance. We can observe a diversification of methods that evaluate ESG performance through various indices, standards, ratings and sustainability frameworks. Nevertheless, ESG indices remain an underexplored object of academic inquiry. This article is conducting a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of ESG indices research within the economics and business literature, based on a dataset of 1420 Scopus-indexed publications. The findings of the systematic overview of the academic literature on ESG indices show an acceleration in scholarly output on ESG indices and citation activity in the post-2020 period, with Covid-19 being a key catalyst. Also, there is a small set of leading finance journals that influence the ESG indices research, and a skewed productivity distribution, between a small number of prolific contributors, and a large number of authors with limited output. The Academic production of output on ESG indices is strongly concentrated in a small group of countries, such as China, The United States, The United Kingdom, India and Italy, followed by a second European core, formed by France, Germany and Spain, that exhibit a balanced publication and citation performance. The findings illustrate promising future research directions on ESG indices, with consequences for academics, investors and policy-makers that need to take into account ESG-performance and investment frameworks.*

Keywords: *ESG Indices; ESG Index; ESG Funds; Bibliometric Analysis.*

1. Introduction

The worldwide growth of corporate sustainability disclosure is driven by increasing stakeholder's demand for greater transparency concerning companies' Environmental, Social and Governance performance. Over the last twenty years, this trend led to the development of multiple sustainability reporting tools, intended to document corporate progress toward sustainability targets. However, the accelerated growth and methodological heterogeneity of these frameworks, standards, ratings and indices have generated significant challenges for stakeholders. A central concern arises from the significant absence of conceptual and methodological harmonization among major ESG rating agencies in defining ESG characteristics, attributes and underlying standards. These divergences in rating criteria frequently result in contradictory evaluations of the same firms, resulting in low levels of consistency across rating providers. Such inconsistencies propagate into investment practices by producing divergent ESG investment universes and consequently, heterogenous benchmarks, thereby significantly

complicating the assessment of asset managers' performance and diluting the influence of investors' sustainability preferences on asset prices.

Several global providers have developed diverse ESG indexes designed to support standardised approaches to environmental, social and governance investing. These tools assist in asset allocation decisions, support portfolio construction and enable comprehensive risk and performance analysis. By providing standardized metrics, they allow investors to integrate environmental, social and governance considerations into investment strategies, establish effective benchmark ESG-oriented investment outcomes and manage, monitor and report ESG related disclosures with increased transparency and consistency. These indices are based on heterogeneous methodological frameworks. Some rely on exclusionary approaches, such as omitting companies involved in controversial weapons or tobacco, while others employ more complex multi-factor scoring systems that adjust constituent weights based on their ESG performance. Key index families and their providers include: MSCI ESG Indexes, S&P Global ESG Indexes, FTSE Russell ESG Indexes, Dow Jones Sustainability Indexes (DJSI), The Nasdaq-100 ESG Index, STOXX ESG Index and EURONEXT ESG Index.

Typically relying on data provided by ESG rating agencies, such as ISS, Sustainalytics or CDP, in order to assess and quantify corporate performance across environmental social and governance dimensions, ESG Indices function as analytical tools that enable the identification, filtering and prioritisation of securities according to their sustainability attributes. An index represents a curated set of companies intended to capture the performance of a specific market segment, whether defined by industry, geographic region, firm size, or sectoral characteristics. Across global financial markets, thousands of sustainability-oriented indices currently exist, encompassing both broad-market ESG benchmarks and thematic indices, targeting specific domains such as renewable energy, water management, or carbon-intensive industries. Some ESG indexes may apply exclusionary rules by omitting firms whose activities conflict with commonly accepted ESG standards (for example, companies engaged in the production of controversial weapons, gambling activities or the extraction and refinement of fossil fuels). Similarly, the exponential development of ESG Indices has been accompanied by a growing academic interest in the analysis of these indices.

In this context, the objective of the present bibliometric study is to assess the extent to which ESG Indices are addressed within the economics and business literature, to identify the main thematic domains and analytical perspectives associated with them, and to map their connections with related research streams such as sustainable finance, investment performance, risk management, and corporate governance. Therefore, this analysis aims to highlight existing gaps in the academic literature and to outline potential directions for future research, thereby contributing to a more structured and comprehensive understanding of ESG Indices as both analytical tools and financial instruments within the sustainable finance ecosystem.

2. Literature Review

The specialized academic literature in the field of sustainability reporting in general, and more recently, of ESG Indices, is extremely vast, regardless of the database in which it is indexed (Scopus or Web of Science). Thus, a bibliometric analysis of the current state of the literature is more than necessary, as it provides a systematization of the information already published, identifies research gaps and outlines future directions for investigation. Literature reviews are essential for mapping and valuating existing knowledge, yet traditional narrative approaches often lack rigor, transparency and practical relevance, resulting in biased and fragmented insights that weaken evidence-based decision-making (Tranfield et al., 2003.) Recently, there has been noticed a growing interest in bibliometric analyses (Donthu et al., 2021; Gao et al., 2021). The availability of major scientific databases such as Scopus and Web of Science, together with analytical tools like Vosviewer, the Biblioshiny package R, CiteSpce has facilitated the collection and analysis of bibliometric data. As a multidisciplinary approach that integrates quantification, mathematics, statistical and philology (Gao et al., 2021), focusing on measurable elements such as publication output, citation patterns, authorship and vocabulary structures, bibliometric analysis enables the effective management of large bodies of scientific literature and enhances the impact of literature reviews. At the same time, it facilitates a deeper understanding of the evolutionary dynamics of a given field while simultaneously identifying its emerging research areas

(Donthu et al., 2021). Literature performance can be assessed through citation metrics, while scientific mapping techniques enable the visualization of the structural relationship and evolution of a research field. To this end, citation and co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling and keyword co-occurrence analysis are employed to evaluate scholarly influence, thematic similarity and emerging research hotspot. (Gao et al., 2021).

Siew (2015) provides a comprehensive review of corporate sustainability reporting tools (SRTs), which companies use to disclose their ESG performance. The paper classifies SRTs into three main groups: frameworks, standards and ratings & indices. Frameworks, such as GRI, SIGMA, DPSIR, CDP, WBCSD, provide overarching principles and guidelines that support companies organise and communicate sustainability information. Standards, including AA1000, SA8000, ISO 14001, ISO 9001 EMAS, are more formalised instruments that focus on best practices for environmental quality and social management system. Ratings and indices, such as KLD, ERIS, SAM/DJSI, FTSE, MSCI ESG Indices, Bloomberg ESG scores, evaluate and benchmark corporate ESG performance, primarily for investment decision-making. The paper also identifies several challenges in sustainability reporting, including a lack of standardisation across tools, methodological inconsistencies, risk of greenwashing and limited quantitative rigor of many criteria, all of which hinder comparability among companies and contribute to distorted assessments of their actual sustainability performance. An interesting relationship between the CSR performance and the readability of CSR disclosures was analysed by Wang et al. (2018), using a hand-collected sample of 331 CSR reports from U.S. public companies. Findings suggest that companies with superior CSR performance produce more readable CSR reports, particularly in relation to social performance, thereby facilitating investors' assessment of CSR disclosures and highlighting the need for greater regulatory attention to the narrative presentation of CSR information.

Despite Social Impact Bonds (SIB) growing prominence, empirical and theoretical evidence on the effectiveness, benefits and limitations of SIBs remains limited, while data on both completed and ongoing projects is insufficient and subject to weak disclosure requirements (Walker et al., 2023). Given the largely thematic and fragmented nature of existing research, Walker (2023) undertakes a systematic analytical review of the SIB literature and landscape. The study examines sources indexed in Scopus and Google Scholar, combining peer-reviewed academic studies with relevant grey literature that covers publications from 2010 and 2021. The findings suggest that the literature is rapidly shifting toward theoretical analyses of a financial instrument that remains in its formative stage, while providing limited empirical support. Investigating whether socially responsible investing (SRI) has any effect on portfolio performance, utilizing companies' ESG-based scores of stocks located in Europe and Turkey, Zehir & Aibars (2020) find that there is no significant impact of SRI on portfolio performance in the period of 2004 - 2018. While the majority of studies focus on ESG performance or address divergences in sustainability reporting, rating and scores, there is a relatively limited number of studies that analyse the literature on ESG Indices from a bibliometric analysis' s perspective.

A bibliometric analysis of climate investing conducted by Joshi and Dash (2023) concludes that the United States is the leading contributor to scholarly output in this field, followed by the United Kingdom, Australia and China. Excepting China and India, emerging market economies contribute only marginally to climate investing research, resulting in a pronounced concentration of academic output in developed countries and highlighting a significant research gap in emerging economies. Keyword-based analysis identifies the core thematic dimensions of climate investing research, as "climate change", "climate investing", "carbon dioxide", "sustainable development" and "decision-making". Related subthemes include environmental policy, investment dynamics, greenhouse gas emissions and emission control. Furthermore, cluster analysis reveals several prominent research streams, notably risk assessment, adaptive management, the formulation and implementation of environmental and energy policies and strategies aimed at reducing reliance on fossil within the context of climate investing. Aiming to systematically examine and visually mapping the academic discourse on core ESG dimensions from a bibliometric perspective, with particular emphasis on the relationship between ESG and performance, Khurshid and Islam (2025) conducted a comprehensive bibliometric analysis on the ESG literature. Using the Biblioshiny package R, the analysis covers 785 documents indexed in the Scopus database, published across 295 journals between 1992 and 2023. The results identify ESG

impact on performance, ESG investing, performance measurement and corporate sustainability as the dominant research themes, while the effects of ESG on fund performance and green technology emerge as an evolving area of inquiry.

Analysing trends in environmental information disclosure (EID), An et al. (2025) examines EID research from 1992 to 2024 using mapping techniques implemented through VOS viewer and the Biblioshiny package in R. The findings reveal a sustained growth in EID-related publications and citations, with continued expansion expected, identify leading journals and authors in the field, and highlight niche and motor themes - along with ESG performance, digital transformation and green innovation - as key focal areas for future research across countries and industries. A bibliometric analysis of ESG literature, addressing key themes, influential authors and future research directions performed by Ahuja and Rani (2025) reveals four core research streams: ESG investing, ESG disclosure and integrated reporting, ESG performance and firm value and a ESG performance and corporate governance.

Since the 1970s the concept of Socially Responsible Investing (SRI) has emerged as a distinct approach for investors. SRI integrates financial objectives with ethical considerations, integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria to invest in companies that generate social and environmental benefits, while excluding those engaged in harmful products or practices. Researching socially responsible investing (SRI), Deepmala et al. (2022) concluded that, despite the significant expansion of the academic literature in the field in recent years, yet comprehensive syntheses remain limited. Addressing this gap, a bibliometric study, applying VOS viewer and Biblioshiny to 1,073 Scopus-indexed articles published since 1985 identifies the main research directions and current dynamics of the SRI literature, highlighting the most influential publications, authors, and sources. The analysis shows that SRI research primarily focuses on the performance of socially responsible investment, green finance, CSR - SRI - firm performance linkages, while also outlining key challenges and future research directions. Other bibliometric analyses of the existing literature identify strong linkages between the concepts of “Sustainable Finance” and keywords like “ESG” and “sustainable development” (Kumar and Pandey, 2026), offering insights into how alternative finance mechanisms contribute to sustainable development (Fatima & Levi, 2026). The gap between national ESG performance has gradually increasing overtime, while an overall upward global trend, particularly among high-income countries was observed (Jiang et al., 2024).

Nevertheless, despite the substantial and rapidly growing body of literature addressing sustainability performance and ESG-related outcomes, a bibliometric analysis explicitly focused on ESG Indices has not been clearly identified in recent scholarly research. While numerous studies examine ESG performance, ratings, disclosure, and responsible investment more broadly, the specific role of ESG indices, despite their proliferation and continuous development, has received limited systematic and integrative attention.

3. Data and Methodology

To evaluate scholarly advancement and examine the dynamics of knowledge development in the ESG Indices domain, a bibliometric analysis was conducted using the Scopus database and VOS viewer (version 1.6.19). This study adopted a Boolean search strategy to retrieve relevant publications related to ESG Indices. Specifically, the “AND” and “OR” operators were applied to systematically refine and expand the search within the database, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the relevant literature. The search targeted the *Article Title*, *Abstract*, and *Keywords* fields and was first based on the following advanced query: *(TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG Indexes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG Indices) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG Funds)) AND PUBYEAR > 1979 AND PUBYEAR < 2026*.

The initial search yielded 2,505 records, spanning a period of more than four decades. The dataset was subsequently refined through the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Twenty-three records with undefined authors (primarily book chapters) were excluded. The subject areas were restricted to Business, Management and Accounting; Economics, Econometrics and Finance, which together accounted for over 80% of the initially retrieved documents. Document types were limited to articles, books and book chapters, while conference papers, review articles, retracted documents, errata, and notes were excluded, considering their limited relevance to the research objective. The publication stage

was restricted to final versions, excluding article in press, and only English-language publications were retained. As the analysis was conducted in December 2025, publications dated 2025 were included. At the same time, 7 articles with publication date 2026 were excluded. Considering all the exclusion and inclusion criteria, the query was (TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG Indexes) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG INDICES) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (ESG FUNDS)) AND (EXCLUDE (PREFNAMEAUID , "undefined")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ECON") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "BUSI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE , "final")).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Source: generated using PRISMA Flow Diagram tool

The final dataset, whose selection is illustrated in Figure 1, comprised 1422 eligible articles. These records were examined using a combined analytical approach that integrated descriptive statistical analyses of publication and citation patterns, by year, journal, subject area, author, and country, employing Scopus's *Analyze Search Results* and *Citation Overview* tools, alongside the analysis of bibliometric network visualizations generated using VOS viewer. This study employed two widely used bibliometric methodologies, performance analysis and scientific mapping, to examine the literature and assess the thematic coherence of the field. Accordingly, two complementary levels of analysis were conducted: first, a preliminary performance analysis of the retrieved documents using Scopus's *Analyze Search Results* tool, included publication metrics, such as authors, institutions, nations, journals, source,

affiliation, country/territory, subject area, and funding sponsor. Second, a more comprehensive scientific mapping analysis carried out with VOS viewer illustrates the structure and dynamics of the topic, using various tools, such as citation analysis, co-citation analysis, keyword occurrence analysis, and co-authorship analysis. Although the two types of analysis can, and in most cases are presented separately, in certain situations, such as citation analysis or author analysis, their successive presentation from both a descriptive statistical perspective and a scientific mapping perspective can provide a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the analysed field.

4. Results

4.1. Document analysis

The first article in the field of ESG Indexes was published in 2009 by Swidler and Crutchley (2009). The study argues that if corporate sustainability enhances firm value, corporate boards should promote strategies that address environmental, social and governance risk. Using U.S. firms included in the Dow Jones Global Sustainability Index as a proxy for sustainability, the findings show that although sustainable firms exhibit higher average returns and initially higher valuation ratios than large-cap and industry-matched peers, their risk-adjusted performance and risk levels do not significantly differ from comparable firms, and valuation advantages tend to converge over time, suggesting a broader diffusion of sustainability practices across firms.

Figure 2. Documents distribution by year

Source: generated using Scopus's Analyse Search Results tool

As illustrated in Figure 2, the yearly evolution of publications on ESG Indices can be divided into four distinct phases. During the initial period (2009-2014), scholarly output remained limited, with fewer than ten articles published per year. This was followed by a moderate expansion over the subsequent five years, when annual publications increased to approximately 10-20 articles. A further acceleration is observed in the period 2020-2022, marked by a steady rise in scientific output. Most notably, the final phase reveals a pronounced surge in specialized literature, culminating in more than 400 articles published in 2025 alone. Table 1 presents the annual share of publications and the corresponding year-to-year growth indices, indicating that over the past five years, academic output has increased at an average annual rate of approximately 50%. The most pronounced increase in the number of publications is observed in 2020 compared with 2019, when scholarly output rose by a factor of 2.34. This surge may be associated with the COVID-19 pandemic, a period during which environmental and social issues gained heightened prominence in both public and academic discourse, a period during which environmental, social, and governance considerations gained heightened prominence in both public debate and academic research. The pandemic exposed systemic vulnerabilities related to social resilience, environmental risk, and corporate governance, contributing to a rapid shift in investor

preferences toward ESG indices, thereby accelerating scholarly interest in ESG-related topics. In parallel, the post-2020 period was characterized by intensified regulatory initiatives, including the EU Sustainable Finance Action Plan, the EU Taxonomy Regulation, and expanding ESG disclosure requirements, which further stimulated academic engagement.

Table 1. The Documents evolution by year

Year	Documents	The annual share of documents %	$I_{i/i-1}$
2009	1	0,07%	-
2010	3	0,21%	3
2011	4	0,28%	1,33
2012	5	0,35%	1,25
2013	6	0,42%	1,20
2014	9	0,63%	1,50
2015	11	0,77%	1,22
2016	18	1,27%	1,64
2017	20	1,41%	1,11
2018	28	1,97%	1,40
2019	29	2,04%	1,04
2020	68	4,78%	2,34
2021	76	5,34%	1,12
2022	146	10,27%	1,92
2023	213	14,98%	1,46
2024	355	24,96%	1,67
2025	430	30,24%	1,21
TOTAL	1422	100%	1,46

Source: Generated using data from Scopus's Analyse Search Results tool

4.2. Source analysis

Analysing the distribution of documents by source reveals that at least two documents of those analysed were published in each of 151 sources, which together account for 441 publications. Given the large number of journals involved, the analysis is further narrowed to the top 10 of the most important publications, ranked by the number of published documents, are further analysed, with these journals collectively containing approximately 25% of the articles included in the sample. These are reported in Table 2, which presents the number of articles published by each source, their relative contribution to the total set of journals, and key indicators of journal performance, including: Cite Score, SJR and SNIP metric for 2025.

Table 2. The Documents distribution by sources

Source	Number of Documents	Citations	The share of Documents %	D/C	2025 Performance Statistic		
					Cite Score	SJR	SNIP
"Finance Research Letters"	70	1448	5%	20,69	10,7	1,711	1,918
"Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment"	47	1314	3%	27,96	14,4	1,146	1,518

“International Review of Financial Analysis”	46	1013	3%	22,02	11,1	2,288	2,422
“Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management”	42	1834	3%	43,67	14,7	2,294	2,541
“Business Strategy and the Environment”	29	1628	2%	56,14	23,7	3,609	3,191
“Journal of Risk and Financial Management”	29	280	2%	9,66	5,5	0,48	0,906
“Journal of Cleaner Production”	25	1562	2%	62,48	20,7	2,174	2,231
“International Review of Economics and Finance”	23	355	2%	15,43	7,3	1,372	1,829
“Research in International Business and Finance”	23	433	2%	18,83	11,1	1,415	1,869
“Journal of Asset Management”	21	184	1%	8,76	3,2	0,478	0,842
Other Journals	1067		75%				
Total	1422		100%				

Source: Generated using data from Scopus’s Analyse Search Results tool

Regarding the publication outlets, Figure 3 indicates a pronounced acceleration in scholarly output beginning in 2020, mirroring the overall exponential growth of the field. “*Finance Research Letters*” emerges as the leading source, accounting for the highest number of publications (70 articles) over the analysed period, with a notable concentration of outputs after 2020. In 2025 alone, the journal published 31 relevant documents, underscoring its central role in disseminating ESG-related research. This prominence is further reflected in its bibliometric performance indicators, including a Cite Score of 10.7, which captures the average citation impact per document, a Sc imago Journal Rank (SJR) of 1.711, indicating strong scientific influence adjusted for journal prestige, and a Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP) of 1.918, reflecting high contextual citation impact relative to the field.

Figure 3. Documents Distribution by Source. Top Ten Leading Source

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results

To provide an overview of the performance of the top 10 sources in which the analysed documents were published, Table 3 reports their annual bibliometric performance indicators, namely Cite Score, SJR, and SNIP, as provided by Scopus’s Analyse Search Results for the top ten leading sources. Cite Score reflects the average number of citations received per document published in a journal over a defined period, offering an indication of its overall citation impact. The Sc imago Journal Rank (SJR) indicator accounts for both the number of citations and the prestige of the citing journals, thereby capturing the scientific influence of a source. Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP) normalizes citation impact across different research fields, enabling meaningful comparisons between journals with varying citation practices.

The citation-source network illustrated in Figure 4 is highlighting the most influential journals and their interrelationships based on citation linkages, revealing a core-periphery structure dominated by a small number of highly cited finance and sustainability journals, surrounded by a wider network of interdisciplinary outlets. A small group of journals emerges as dominant citation hubs.” Finance Research Letters” stands out as the most influential source, exhibiting the largest node, that reflects its role as a key outlet for timely and high-impact research at the intersection of finance and ESG Indices-related topics. Similarly, journals such as the „Journal of Asset Management”, „Journal of Risk and Financial Management”, and the „Journal of Sustainable Finance” occupy central positions, indicating their importance in disseminating influential ESG Indices scholarship. Journals including „Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management”, „Journal of Cleaner Production”, „Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal”, and „Business Strategy and Development” form a closely linked cluster focused on sustainability practices, corporate responsibility, and environmental management. The citation connections within this group suggest a cohesive research stream centered on firm-level ESG practices, disclosure, and sustainability performance.

Table 3. Top Ten Sources Metrics During 2014-2024

Journals	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
	Cite Score										
Finance Research Letters	1,1	0,8	0,8	1,3	2,1	3,8	5,3	9,3	10,8	11,1	10,7
Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment					2	1,9	2,4	4,5	7,4	10,6	14,4
International Review of Financial Analysis	1,4	1,8	2,5	3	3,4	3,8	4,9	7,2	9,1	10,3	11,1
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	5,3	7,2	7,8	6,8	6,5	5,9	8	11,5	15,6	17,2	14,7
Business Strategy and the Environment	6,1	6,3	7,3	7,3	7,6	8,4	10,3	11,9	17,8	22,5	23,7
Journal of Risk and Financial Management									2,8	4,5	5
Journal of Cleaner Production	5,6	6,8	7,4	7,7	8,7	10,9	13,1	15,8	18,5	20,4	20,7
International Review of Economics and Finance	2,3	2,8	2,8	2,8	2,6	3,1	3,6	3,9	5,7	7,3	7,3
Research in International Business and Finance	2	2	2,2	2	2,6	3,7	4,9	6,9	9,1	11,2	11,1
Journal of Asset Management	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,6	0,6	0,6	1	1,8	2,7	4,1	3,2
	SC Imago Journal Rank (SJR)										
Finance Research Letters	0,465	0,397	0,386	0,565	0,77	0,999	1,339	2,007	2,231	1,903	1,711
Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment					0,52	0,668	0,445	0,642	0,897	1,007	1,146
International Review of Financial Analysis	0,536	0,531	0,809	0,755	0,782	0,874	1,27	1,833	1,881	1,832	2,288
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	1,793	2,066	2,43	1,706	1,67	0,974	1,519	1,945	2,134	2,201	2,294
Business Strategy and the Environment	1,782	1,803	2,369	1,881	2,166	1,828	2,123	2,241	2,87	3,666	3,609
Journal of Risk and Financial Management									0,258	0,485	0,48
Journal of Cleaner Production	1,665	1,635	1,659	1,467	1,62	1,886	1,937	1,921	1,981	2,058	2,174
International Review of Economics and Finance	0,852	0,947	0,721	0,841	0,772	0,813	0,781	0,748	0,929	1,093	1,372
Research in International Business and Finance	0,589	0,43	0,7	0,548	0,647	0,638	0,767	1,043	1,273	1,294	1,415
Journal of Asset Management	0,212	0,203	0,208	0,199	0,241	0,242	0,362	0,466	0,482	0,619	0,478
	Source Normalized Impact per Paper (SNIP)										
Finance Research Letters	0,994	0,791	0,711	0,782	0,907	1,432	1,657	2,336	2,508	2,155	1,918
Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment	0,437	0,217	0,592	0,381	1,004	0,692	0,58	1,18	1,834	1,381	1,518

International Review of Financial Analysis	1,154	0,946	1,27	1,33	1,346	1,446	1,707	2,035	2,178	1,918	2,422
Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management	2,107	2,324	2,959	2,476	2,514	1,545	2,222	1,776	2,119	2,305	2,541
Business Strategy and the Environment	1,797	2,106	2,221	2,38	2,622	1,828	2,512	2,025	2,376	2,8	3,191
Journal of Risk and Financial Management							1,103	0,935	0,944	0,853	0,906
Journal of Cleaner Production	2,479	2,401	2,547	2,382	2,295	2,332	2,432	2,36	2,318	2,199	2,231
International Review of Economics and Finance	1,615	1,535	1,284	1,138	1,171	1,305	1,397	1,198	1,432	1,472	1,829
Research in International Business and Finance	1,418	1,308	1,806	1,495	1,062	1,189	1,727	1,57	1,916	1,839	1,869
Journal of Asset Management	0,491	0,506	0,4	0,353	0,386	0,489	0,453	0,754	0,885	0,889	0,842

Source: Generated using data from Scopus's Analyse Search Results Tool

Figure 4. Citation- Source map

Source: VOS viewer

Another cluster is formed around governance and economics-focused outlets, such as „Corporate Governance: An International Review”, „International Review of Economics”, „Applied Economics” and „Energy Economics”. These sources bridge ESG Indices research with broader economic, regulatory and governance debates, highlighting the integration of ESG considerations into mainstream economic and financial analysis. Portfolio Management and Financial Markets including Journals such as the „Journal of Portfolio Management”, „Journal of Investing”, and „Asia-Pacific Financial Markets” are positioned at the intersection of ESG and investment research. Their citation links indicate a growing body of literature examining ESG indices, sustainable investments, and risk-return trade-offs within financial markets. The presence of diverse outlets, including „Sustainable Futures, Innovation and Green Development”, and „Society and Business Review”, demonstrates the interdisciplinary expansion of the field. These journals connect financial and governance-focused research with broader sustainability, innovation, and societal impact perspectives.

4.3. Authors’ analysis

Out of the 3,439 authors who contributed to the 1,422 analysed documents, 160 authors are identified as having authored at least two publications, collectively accounting for 444 documents.

Table 4. Authors Productivity Distribution

Number of Articles	Authors	%
2	87	54%
3	49	31%
4	13	8%
5	6	4%
6	3	2%
9	1	1%
14	1	1%
Grand Total	160	100%

Source: Generated using data from Scopus’s Analyse Search Results tool

Table 4 illustrates the distribution of abovementioned 160 authors by publication output, considering authors who have contributed at least two articles. The findings reveal a small number of highly productive authors and a large proportion of contributors with limited publication output, indicating a strong concentration of output at lower productivity levels. 54% of the authors (87 authors) published two articles, while 31% (49 authors) contributed with three articles. Consequently, over 85% of productive authors fall within the two-three publication range, suggesting recurring but limited participation in the analysed field. As the number of publications increases, the proportion of authors declines sharply: only 8% published four articles, and 6% published five or six articles. Only a very small number of authors demonstrate high productivity, with just two authors (2%) having published nine and fourteen articles, respectively. This distribution reflects a pattern characteristic of academic literature, in which a small core of highly prolific researchers coexists with a large group of moderately productive contributors, indicating a field that is expanding yet still fragmented in terms of sustained individual contributions.

Figure 5. Documents distribution by author. Top authors

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results Tool

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of authors according to publication output, considering only those who have contributed at least five articles to the field. Two authors stand out as highly prolific: Plastun, A., with nine publications, and Makarenko, I., who emerges as the most productive author with fourteen publications.

Co-authorship analysis explores collaborative relationships among the scholar’s interactions in a research field, capturing formal modes of intellectual collaboration among researchers, including associated attributes such as institutional affiliations and countries. (Donthu et al., 2021)

Figure 6. Co-authorship map

Source: VOS viewer

The Co-authorship map network presented in Figure 6 is characterized by a small number of highly central authors who act as collaboration hubs. Makarenko Inna O., affiliated at Sumy State University, Ukraine with 14 articles emerges as the most influential node (red), occupying a central position with extensive co-authorship links across multiple clusters. This positioning indicates a coordinating role in knowledge production and points to strong leadership in collaborative research efforts. Closely connected authors such as Serpeniova Yuliia, Guzhenko Tetiana, Vorontsova Anna, and Makarenko Serhiy M. form a dense sub-network, reflecting sustained and recurrent collaboration within this core group around Sumy State University, Ukraine. Several secondary clusters are visible, each centered around influential authors such as Plastun Alex, affiliated at the same Sumy State University, Ukraine (green); Umar Zaghum, (Zayed University, Dubai, United Arab Emirates) (turquoise); Bhattacharjee Purba (Goa Institute Management (GIM), India), and Bouri Elie (Lebanese American University, Beirut, Lebanon) (violet). These clusters appear relatively cohesive internally but are more loosely connected to the main core. Notably, Umar, Zaghum and Bouri, Elie functions as a bridging author, linking otherwise separate collaboration groups and facilitating knowledge exchange across thematic or geographical boundaries.

A small peripheral cluster (orange) emerges around Kang, Sang-Hoon (Pusan National, Busan, South Korea) and Belghouthi Housseem Eddine (Université de Tunis El Manar, Tunis, Tunisia.) This cluster represents a highly specialized and narrowly focused collaboration within the broader co-authorship network. Its limited size and weak links to other clusters indicate marginal integration into the main collaborative cores of ESG research. The cluster is characterized by strong internal ties, reflecting recurrent collaboration among the same authors, and low external connectivity, suggesting minimal co-authorship with the wider ESG scholarly community, yet highlighting opportunities for broader international and interdisciplinary collaboration to strengthen the cohesion and resilience of ESG scholarship.

4.4. Leading Countries in ESG Indices Research

The geographic distribution of publications reveals a highly unbalanced global landscape of research activity across countries in the analysed field, indicating significant regional disparities in scholarly output. While the overall volume of publications is concentrated in a limited number of leading countries, the majority of nations contribute only modestly to the literature.

Figure 7. Documents distribution by country

Source: Scopus's Analyse Search Results Tool

The geographic distribution of publications represented in Figure 7 reveals a highly unbalanced global landscape of research activity across countries in the analysed field, indicating significant regional disparities in scholarly output. While the overall volume of publications is concentrated in a limited number of leading countries, the majority of nations contribute only modestly to the literature.

According to the dates provided by Analyse Search Results Tool, presented in Figure 8, 76 out of 84 countries, representing 90,5% fall within the 1-50 articles range, indicating that most countries exhibit relatively low research output in the field. Only three counties (Australia, Spain and France), representing 3,6% published between 51 and 100 articles, while even smaller number of countries reached higher levels of productivity: Two countries (Italy and United Kingdom), representing 2,4% produced between 100 and 150 articles and three countries (United States, India and China), representing the rest of 3,6 % exceed 150 publications. The predominance of developed countries among the top 20 contributors suggests that advanced economic development facilitates stronger engagement with environmental and corporate governance research. Considering the leading countries in ESG Indices Research, Table 5 presents a list of top 15 countries that have produced a substantial number of documents in this area, ranked according to the total number of citations.

Figure 8. Documents distribution by country. Top 15 countries

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results Tool

Table 5. Leading Countries in ESG Indices Research

Country	Documents	Citations	C/D
United States	168	5542	32,99
United Kingdom	126	4987	39,58
Italy	123	3663	29,78
China	180	3361	18,67
France	79	2496	31,59
Australia	56	2338	41,75
India	168	2063	12,28
Canada	47	1572	33,45
Spain	65	1533	23,58
Germany	45	1390	30,89
Netherlands	25	1364	54,56
Denmark	13	1156	88,92
United Arab Emirates	30	1059	35,30
Brazil	24	1011	42,13
Tunisia	39	874	22,41
Pakistan	22	850	38,64
Malaysia	49	793	16,18
Russian Federation	29	779	26,86
Greece	29	761	26,24
Turkey	38	651	17,13

Source: Generated using data from Scopus’s Analyse Search Results tool

To complement the analysis, a citation map generated using VOS viewer is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Citation- country map

Source: VOS viewer

When the country-level bibliometric indicators are examined alongside the VOS viewer country map, a coherent picture emerges regarding both the volume of research output and the spatial positioning of countries within the global ESG research landscape. The findings highlight a strong concentration of academic production among small group of countries: China, India, United States, United Kingdom and Italy. These leading contributors account for a disproportionate share of total publications, where the vast majority of countries remaining play a marginal role in ESG Indices related academic research. Although the presence of emerging economies among the top contributors shows a gradual diversification on the research landscape, the dominance of a few countries continues to shape the global ESG Index research agenda, pointing significant opportunities for future research to incorporate perspectives from underrepresented regions.

As shown in Figure 10, The United States, China, and the United Kingdom clearly dominate in terms of both document volume and citation impact. China stands out as the most productive country in terms of publications, with 180 documents and 3,361 citations, confirming its rapid expansion in ESG-related research and strong institutional support for ESG scholarship. The United States records one of the highest citation counts, reflecting not only prolific output but also strong international visibility while United Kingdom also occupy central positions in the network, combining high publication volumes with substantial citation impact, illustrating their role as global knowledge hubs. India ranks among the top contributors in terms of document volume (168 publications), although its citation count (2,063 citations) reflects a comparatively lower average impact per publication than that of China, the United States, or Western European countries. This pattern points to rapid quantitative expansion accompanied by a still-developing citation profile.

Several European countries, including France (79 documents; 2,496 citations), Germany (45 documents; 1,390 citations), Italy, and Spain, form a strong secondary core. These countries exhibit a relatively balanced relationship between publication output and citation impact, indicating mature research ecosystems with sustained international visibility. Smaller European contributors such as Belgium (17 documents; 628 citations), Denmark (13 documents; 1,1156 citations), and Greece (29 documents; 761 citations) demonstrate fewer publications but comparatively high citation counts, showing a higher average impact and specialization within niche research areas. In contrast, several countries, including Tunisia, Pakistan, Malaysia, Greece, Turkey, and the Russian Federation appear with smaller nodes therefore being characterized by limited publication output and lower citation

counts. These include several emerging and developing economies across Africa, the Middle East, and parts of Asia. While their presence indicates growing global engagement with ESG Indices topics, their lower citation counts and marginal placement in the map indicate more limited international visibility and weaker integration into global collaboration structures.

Figure 10. Documents distribution by country. Top 15 countries

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results Tool

Figure 11. Documents distribution by funding sponsor. Top 15 sponsors

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results Tool

The ranking of top funding sponsors, presented in Figure 11, led by institutions, such as the National Natural Science Foundation of China, point to a strong concentration of research funding among a small group of highly influential organizations, predominantly based in China. This concentration likely plays a significant role in shaping global research output patterns in the ESG field, reinforcing the prominence of countries with well-established and strategically aligned funding infrastructures. The distribution of documents by funding sponsor further, presented in Table 6, reinforces this concentration. The vast majority of funding sponsors (145 out of 160, representing 90%) are associated with a relatively small number of publications - between 1 and 5 articles - illustrating a highly fragmented funding landscape at the lower end. In contrast, only a very limited number of sponsors support a larger volume of research,

with 9 sponsors (6%) funding between 6 and 10 articles, and progressively fewer sponsors contributing to higher publication ranges.

Table 6. The Documents distribution by funding sponsor

Documents by funding sponsor	Number of Sponsors	%
1-5	145	91%
6-10	9	6%
11-15	3	2%
16-20	2	1%
56-60	1	1%
Grand Total	160	100%

Source: Generated using data from Scopus's Analyse Search Results tool

4.5. Citation Analysis

Citation dynamics, presented in Figure 12, evolve in tandem with the increase in scholarly publications, revealing a strongly accelerating trajectory in both scholarly output and academic impact. Citations increased exponentially after 2018, rising from 595 in 2020 to 13,179 in 2025. The compound annual growth rate of citations over this five-year period is estimated at approximately 86%, underscoring not only an increase in research volume but also a rapid amplification of scholarly influence and knowledge diffusion. The strongest citation acceleration occurred between 2021 and 2022, when the year-to-year growth index peaked at 2.44, reflecting the consolidation of ESG Index research as a central theme in finance, sustainability, and policy-oriented scholarship. In Table 7 the top ten leading Cited Articles are presented.

Citation analysis is a fundamental science-mapping technique grounded in the premise that citations represent intellectual connections between scholarly works, formed when one publication references another. Within this framework, a publication's influence is proxied by the number of citations it accumulates. Accordingly, citation analysis enables the identification of the most impactful and influential contributions within a given research domain (Donthu et al., 2021). Furthermore, co-citation analysis is based on the assumption that publication frequently cited together share thematic or conceptual similarity. This approach is widely used to uncover the intellectual structure of a research field, revealing its core knowledge bases and dominant thematic areas (Liu et al., 2015). The co-citation analysis was performed, using cited references. 44 items were identified of the 8018 cited references, which were grouped into four distinct clusters.

The co-citation-reference map presented in Figure 13 highlights a well-structured and cumulative knowledge base. ESG Indices research is rooted in early SRI and performance studies, expanded through methodological debates on ESG scoring and divergence, and increasingly connected to disclosure, governance, and regional applications. The strong inter-cluster connectivity confirms that ESG Indices function as a conceptual nexus, integrating measurement issues with financial performance and sustainability outcomes.

The green cluster, anchored by classic works such as Bauer et al., Bollen, Becchetti, Brammer, and Friede captures research focused on sustainable and socially responsible investing, with strong links to ESG Indices, ETFs, and capital market dynamics. It emphasizes investment performance, risk, and return, reflecting how ESG-based instruments are integrated into portfolio management and financial markets. The yellow cluster, including Berg et al., Billio, Alda, and Ammann, concentrates on ESG ratings, aggregate confusion, fund scores, and methodological challenges. The dense internal links reflect a growing body of work addressing inconsistencies and comparability issues in ESG Indices - an area of direct relevance to ESG Index construction and evaluation.

Figure 12. Citation evolution

Source: Scopus’s Analyse Search Results Tool

Table 7. Leading Cited Articles during 2020-2025

Document	Author	Publication Year	Citation by Year							Total
			<2020	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	
Total			673	595	1045	2550	4136	8579	13179	30736
“Responsible investing: The ESG-efficient frontier”	Pedersen, Lasse Heje Fitzgibbons Shauna; Pomorski, Lukasz	2021	0	0	11	94	176	290	381	952
“Sensitive industries produce better ESG performance: Evidence from emerging markets”	Garcia, Alexandre Sanches Mendes-Da-Silva, Wesleyb; Orsato, Renato	2017	15	26	40	89	106	167	184	627
“Integrating Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Disclosure for a Sustainable Development: An Australian Study”	Lokuwaduge, Chitra Sriyani De Silva Heenetigala Kumudinib	2017	24	25	27	62	70	122	120	450

“ESG Integration and the Investment Management Process: Fundamental Investing Reinvented”	van Duuren, Emiela; Plantinga, Aukea; Scholtens, Bert	2016	34	17	39	61	91	100	99	441
“Socially responsible funds and market crises”	Nofsinger, John Varma, Abhishek	2014	77	35	39	58	74	86	60	426
“Board gender diversity and ESG disclosure: evidence from the USA”	Manita, Riadha Bruna, Maria Giuseppinab Dang, Reyc Houanti, L’Hocined	2018	7	15	20	50	65	123	142	422
“ESG Rating Disagreement and Stock Returns”	Gibson Brandon, Rajnaa; Krueger, Philippb; Schmidt, Peter Steffen	2021	0	0	0	24	49	117	194	384
“Inside the ESG ratings: (Dis)agreement and performance”	Billio, Monicaa Costola, Michelea; Hristova, Ivaa; Latino, Carmelob; Pelizzon, Loriana	2021	0	0	0	16	50	129	169	364
“Transparency among S&P 500 companies: an analysis of ESG disclosure scores”	Tamimi, Nabil, Sebastianelli, Rose	2017	13	17	26	41	67	87	105	356
“Green bonds for sustainable development: Review of literature on development and impact of green bonds”	Bhutta, Umair Saeeda Tariq, Adeelb Farrukh, Muhammadc Raza, Alid; Iqbal, Muhammad Khalid	2022	0	0	0	12	54	115	135	316

Source: Generated using data from Scopus’s Analyse Search Results tool

Figure 13. Co-citation -references analysis

Source: VOSviewer

The red cluster groups more recent and specialized references such as Aydogmus, Alareeni, and Alsayegh, which focus on ESG disclosure, corporate governance, and regional or sector-specific evidence. Its relative separation suggests a newer, more applied research stream that builds upon, rather than defines, the core theoretical foundations. The blue cluster represents the central and bridging literature, connected references such as Albuquerque et al., Amir-Zadeh, and Broadstock. It integrates ESG performance, risk, and financial market outcomes. Their central position indicates that these studies are frequently cited alongside multiple thematic streams, suggesting a unifying role in linking ESG disclosure, performance, and valuation debates.

4.6. Keywords Analysis

In line with co-citation analysis, co-word analysis is based on the assumption that terms that frequently co-occur within documents are thematically related. By using words as the unit of analysis, this approach enables the identification of conceptual structures and dominant research themes within a field (Donthu et al., 2021).

The keyword co-occurrence map was generated using VOS viewer, with a keyword occurrence threshold set to 5, as presented in Figure 14, in a full counting mode. Of all 3351 authors' keywords, 197 terms were identified as meeting the threshold of appearing in at least five documents. Six distinct clusters have emerged, with 2110 links and 3534 total link strength. The core cluster (yellow) is anchored by the keywords "ESG" and "sustainability", indicating their role as the conceptual backbone of the literature. Closely connected other keywords, such as "corporate sustainability", "social responsibility", "GRI", "SDGs", "transparency", and "content analysis" reflect a strong focus on measurement frameworks, reporting standards, and normative foundations of ESG. The green cluster is particularly relevant to ESG Indices, featuring "ESG funds", "ESG indices", "ETFs", "returns", "portfolio choice", "stock markets", and "volatility spillover". This stream focuses on market-based ESG instruments, risk-return dynamics, and portfolio optimization. The presence of econometric methods indicates a quantitative orientation, positioning ESG Indices as operational tools for investors rather than purely normative constructs. The red cluster emphasizes corporate-level ESG mechanisms,

investment benchmarks. The bibliometric analysis reveals that research on ESG Indices, ESG funds, and ESG Indexes is not confined to a single thematic cluster, but rather spans several interconnected clusters, reflecting the multidimensional role these instruments play in the ESG literature.

The finance and market-oriented cluster is directly centred on ESG Indices, ESG funds, ETFs, returns, portfolio choice, stock markets, volatility, and risk modelling techniques (e.g., GARCH, spillover effects). This cluster conceptualizes ESG Indices primarily as investment tools, used to assess risk-return trade-offs, portfolio diversification, and market efficiency. A performance and investment evaluation cluster links ESG Indices and ESG scores with financial performance, firm value, cost of capital, cost of debt, and sustainable investing, where ESG Indices function as measurement instruments that translate corporate ESG characteristics into quantifiable metrics. The governance, disclosure, and measurement cluster incorporates ESG ratings, ESG scores, non-financial reporting, disclosure, indicators, and textual analysis. Within this stream, ESG Indices are examined from a methodological and institutional perspective, focusing on how they are constructed, the consistency and divergence across rating providers, and their dependence on corporate disclosure quality. This cluster highlights ongoing debates regarding comparability, transparency, and reliability of ESG Index methodologies. The emerging and dynamic research cluster connects ESG funds and ESG Indices to COVID-19, climate risk, innovation, fintech, and artificial intelligence. This strand explores how ESG-based instruments behave under systemic shocks and how advanced analytical tools enhance ESG risk assessment and index construction. It points to the growing importance of ESG Indices in times of market stress and regulatory transformation.

5. Conclusions

Although ESG Indices are increasingly employed in studies on sustainable finance, investment performance, risk management, and corporate governance, they still are an underexplored object of academic inquiry. Instead, they function primarily as analytical tools advanced within broader ESG and sustainability debates. This bibliometric study provides a systematic overview of the academic literature on ESG Indices, offering insights into the evolution, structure, and thematic composition of this rapidly developing research domain. Based on a refined dataset of 1,420 Scopus-indexed publications, the analysis reveals a pronounced acceleration in scholarly output and citation activity, particularly in the post-2020 period, confirming the growing relevance of ESG indices within economics and business research.

The publication trend indicates that ESG Indices research reached maturity, marked by a transition from a marginal topic to a central area of scholarly inquiry, following 2020. The pronounced surge in academic output, evidenced by a 2.4-fold increase in 2020 and an average annual growth rate of approximately 50% over the past five years, illustrates the field's strong sensitivity to external shocks and institutional developments, with the COVID-19 pandemic acting as a key catalyst. The source analysis outlets confirm the rapid consolidation and growing academic relevance of ESG Indices research, particularly after 2020. „*Finance Research Letters*” emerges as the main outlet, combining the highest publication volume with strong bibliometric performance indicators (Cite Score, SJR, and SNIP), thus reflecting its central role in shaping and diffusing ESG Indices - related research.

Citation - source network analysis further reveals a structure dominated by a small group of influential finance and sustainability journals, surrounded by a broader set of interdisciplinary outlets. These patterns reflect both the concentration of scholarly influence within leading finance journals and the interdisciplinary expansion of ESG Indices research across economics, governance, and sustainability domains. The analysis of authorship reveals a highly skewed productivity distribution, characterized by a small core of prolific contributors and a large share of authors with limited output. More than 85% of authors contributed with only two or three publications, indicating recurrent yet modest engagement with ESG Indices research. In contrast, only a very limited number of scholars exhibit sustained productivity, with Makarenko, I. (14 publications) and Plastun, A. (9 publications) standing out as leading contributors. Co-authorship network analysis further confirms a core-periphery collaboration structure. A central cluster, dominated by Makarenko Inna O. and closely affiliated colleagues from Sumy State University, acts as the main collaboration hub, reflecting strong leadership and coordinated knowledge production. Several secondary clusters, centered around authors such as Plastun, Umar,

Bhattacharjee, and Bouri, display internal cohesion but weaker integration with the core, while a small peripheral cluster illustrates highly specialized yet isolated collaboration patterns. These findings suggest that ESG Indices research is driven by a limited number of highly connected scholars and research groups, alongside a large base of episodic contributors. This structure highlights both the consolidation of expertise within key hubs and the potential for expanded international and interdisciplinary collaboration to enhance the field's cohesion and long-term development.

Academic production is strongly concentrated in a small group of leading countries, while the vast majority of nations contribute only marginally to this literature. Over 90% of the countries identified fall within the lowest publication range (1-50 articles), illustrating the limited global diffusion of research activity in this domain. At the core of the global research network are China, the United States, the United Kingdom, India, and Italy, which together account for a disproportionate share of publications and citations. China emerges as the most productive contributor, reflecting rapid expansion and strong institutional support, while the United States and the United Kingdom combine high output with substantial citation impact, reinforcing their roles as global knowledge hubs. India's high publication volume is accompanied by a comparatively lower average citation impact, suggesting quantitative growth that has not yet fully translated into scholarly influence. A secondary European core, comprising France, Germany, Italy, and Spain, demonstrates balanced publication and citation performance, indicative of mature research ecosystems. Smaller European countries exhibit fewer publications but relatively high citation impact, pointing to specialization within niche research areas. The strong alignment between country-level output and the geographic distribution of major funding sponsors, particularly the dominance of Chinese institutions, highlights the critical role of funding structures in shaping the global ESG indices research agenda and reflects opportunities to broaden participation from underrepresented regions.

Citation trends closely track the growth in scholarly output, exhibiting a sharply accelerating trajectory in both research volume and academic impact. Citations increase with an estimated compound annual growth rate of approximately 86%, reflecting rapid knowledge diffusion and rising scholarly influence. The keyword cluster analysis indicates that ESG Indices research has evolved into a mature yet diversified field, characterized by multiple interconnected thematic streams rather than a single dominant focus. While sustainability, disclosure and governance remain foundational, the literature has increasingly shifted toward ESG Indices, ESG funds, and market-based applications, reflecting their growing relevance in financial decision-making and risk management. ESG Indices emerge as a central integrative element across clusters. In finance-oriented clusters, they are conceptualized primarily as investment and benchmarking tools used to evaluate risk-return trade-offs, portfolio diversification, and market efficiency. In performance-oriented research, ESG Indices and scores function as quantifiable proxies linking corporate ESG characteristics to firm value, cost of capital, and investment outcomes. Findings illustrate a clear research gap concerning the conceptualization, methodological construction, and comparability of ESG Indices. Addressing these gaps represents a promising avenue for future research, with important implications for academics, investors, and policymakers seeking to enhance the robustness and interpretability of ESG-based investment frameworks.

Despite its comprehensive scope, this study is subject to several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the analysis is based exclusively on the Scopus database, which, although extensive and widely used, does not capture all relevant publications indexed in other databases such as Web of Science, SSRN, or Google Scholar. As a result, some relevant studies, particularly recent working papers or region-specific journal, may be underrepresented. Moreover, the analysis focuses on English-language publications within economics and business subject areas, which may limit insights from interdisciplinary research or non-English scholarship, particularly from underrepresented regions. The selection of the Scopus database was restricted to the Economics and Business domains, without incorporating other closely related fields such as sustainability studies, engineering and social and environmental sciences. These domains may include additional relevant contributions addressing ESG indices from technological, environmental or societal perspectives, which were not captured within the scope of the present analysis. The bibliometric approach relies on metadata (titles, abstracts, keywords, citations) rather than full-text analysis. Consequently, the depth of thematic interpretation is constrained by authors' keyword choices and indexing practices, which may vary across journals and disciplines.

Citation-based indicators may also favour older publications and well-established journals, potentially biasing the identification of influential works. Although ESG Indices are examined as a research object, the study does not differentiate in depth between specific index providers or methodologies, which could be addressed in future comparative or qualitative research.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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